

SallyEval: A Scalable Evaluation System for Ranking LLMs with Qualitative Feedback

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Abstract. Large Language Models (LLMs) are widely used across various applications, yet their performance varies significantly depending on the task. Some models excel in reasoning, while others perform better in language understanding or factual accuracy, making it challenging to determine the most suitable LLM for specific use cases. To address this, we introduce SallyEval, an evaluation platform designed to identify the optimal LLM for integration into the Sally chatbot, an AI system that assists migrants in Greece. SallyEval employs A/B testing with human preference-based scoring, incorporating Elo rating and adaptive sampling to efficiently rank models based on real-world user interactions. In evaluations, the top-performing model, GPT4o-Latest, achieved an Elo score of 1050, with a 64% win rate. Unlike traditional pairwise comparisons that solely determine a winning response, SallyEval enhances the evaluation process by allowing evaluators to provide detailed feedback through a rating scale that covers multiple qualitative assessment criteria, such as accuracy, contextual relevance, clarity, and conciseness, while also supporting custom benchmarking for domain-specific evaluations.

1 Introduction

AI-powered chatbots are becoming increasingly common, helping people find information and receive support in various fields. Large Language Models (LLMs) like GPT-4o, Claude and Gemini have made chatbots more capable than ever, allowing for natural and informative conversations. However, the effectiveness of a chatbot depends heavily on the specific task, domain and language requirements. While some models excel in reasoning and factual accuracy, others perform better in handling multilingual queries. This variation is particularly critical in applications where language plays a major role in user experience.

One such application is migration support, where AI chatbots assist individuals in navigating complex legal procedures, social services, government regulations, and more. These systems must provide clear and accurate information to

users with diverse backgrounds and needs. Selecting the most suitable LLM for this domain is challenging, as existing benchmarks are often too general or rely on static datasets that overlook real-world user preferences [13].

Despite rapid progress in LLM development, the evaluation of these models remains an open research problem. Traditional benchmarks are based on predefined data sets with static questions and ground truth answers, such as MMLU [10], GSM-8K [4], and HellaSwag [11]. While these benchmarks provide useful quantitative insights, they fail to assess the effectiveness of LLMs in dynamic, real-world chatbot interactions, where user preferences play a crucial role. Furthermore, benchmarks that focus on factual accuracy do not account for conversational aspects, such as clarity and contextual adaptation, which are essential for user satisfaction. Beyond these challenges, the rapid evolution of LLMs further complicates the evaluation process, with new models being released frequently. Keeping evaluation frameworks up to date requires constant adaptation, and evaluating LLMs is often slow and resource-intensive.

To address these challenges, we introduce **SallyEval**, a systematic evaluation pipeline designed to compare and rank LLMs for integration into **SALLY**, a chatbot developed to assist migrants in Greece. The primary goal of this work is to identify the most suitable LLM to power SALLY by evaluating multiple models based on their ability to provide accurate, clear, and contextually relevant responses to migration-related queries. SallyEval’s evaluation pipeline can be used by AI researchers, developers, data scientists, and organizations seeking to assess LLMs for diverse real-world applications. Unlike static benchmarks, SallyEval employs a pairwise human preference evaluation framework, leveraging A/B testing, Elo rating, and adaptive sampling to efficiently rank LLMs based on real interactions. While our approach builds upon recent advancements in LLM evaluation methodologies, such as Chatbot Arena’s pairwise human preference ranking system [3], SallyEval extends this framework to address key limitations by focusing on **domain-specific assessment criteria** and qualitative feedback mechanisms, which are essential for evaluating the underlying LLMs used in task-specific applications like SALLY. In contrast, SallyEval allows for custom qualitative evaluation categories and predefined question sets, making it particularly suitable for applications such as migration support.

The contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- We propose a systematic evaluation pipeline for **LLM comparison**, integrating A/B testing, Elo ranking, and adaptive sampling to identify the best performing model for SALLY.
- We develop a dynamic evaluation framework, allowing users to compare responses from preselected LLMs, upload custom evaluation configurations with domain-specific assessment criteria, and incorporate existing question-answer datasets.
- We demonstrate the use of SallyEval in evaluating the underlying LLMs for their suitability within the SALLY platform, identifying key factors that influence LLM effectiveness in this domain.

2 Related Work

Traditional evaluation methods for conversational systems fall into three main categories: automatic, human, and hybrid approaches

Automatic evaluation methods rely on predefined metrics to assess the performance of language models. Popular metrics such as BLEU, ROUGE and METEOR [5, 6] compare generated responses against reference texts based on n-gram similarity. However, these methods often overlook important aspects like conversation flow, coherence, and contextual relevance, making them less effective for chatbot assessment. More recent approaches incorporate embedding-based similarity measures, such as BERTScore [12] and cosine similarity in vector spaces, providing more context-aware evaluations.

Human evaluation remains the most reliable method for assessing language models, offering qualitative insights into fluency, logical consistency, and user satisfaction. Common techniques include Likert-scale ratings, pairwise A/B testing [7], and user surveys. **A/B testing** is a comparative evaluation approach where users are presented with two responses to the same query, each generated by a different model, without knowing their source. Evaluators then select the response they find superior. Studies indicate that human evaluators prioritize attributes such as clarity, informativeness, and engagement over lexical similarity to reference responses [1].

Hybrid approaches aim to balance scalability and evaluation reliability by integrating automated metrics with human preference judgments. One such approach is the **Elo rating system**, a ranking method originally designed for competitive games, where models are dynamically scored based on head-to-head comparisons. When an evaluator selects a preferred model response, the winning model’s Elo score increases while the losing model’s score decreases [2]. To improve ranking efficiency, many evaluation systems utilize **adaptive sampling**, a technique that dynamically selects which models to compare based on their evaluation confidence. Instead of choosing models randomly, adaptive sampling prioritizes comparisons involving under-tested or closely ranked models. For instance, suppose SallyEval is evaluating three LLMs: Model A, Model B, and Model C. Initially, all models have similar Elo scores due to limited evaluation data. As feedback is collected, Model A consistently outperforms others, while Model C underperforms. Model B, however, has fewer evaluations, making its ranking uncertain. Instead of continuing random pairwise comparisons, SallyEval adaptively selects more comparisons involving Model B against both A and C. This targeted approach reduces uncertainty in ranking, ensuring a more efficient allocation of resources, particularly in large-scale model comparisons [8].

While these evaluation methods are effective for general language model assessment used in chatbots, they often fail to account for the challenges of domain-specific applications, such as legal advisory, healthcare, migration support and others. As a result, there is a growing need for tailored benchmarking approaches that consider task-specific requirements. Several key challenges remain:

- **Lack of task-specific metrics:** Most existing benchmarks, such as MMLU, GSM8K, and HellaSwag, primarily assess coding, mathematics, or general knowledge, rather than accuracy in specialized fields like legal consultation, administrative processes, and migration support.
- **Bias in human evaluation:** User feedback is influenced by personal expectations, cultural factors, and prior chatbot interactions, leading to inconsistencies in assessment outcomes.
- **Scalability limitations:** Large-scale human evaluations require significant time and resources, highlighting the need for hybrid methodologies that combine automated scoring with user-driven feedback.

To bridge these gaps, SallyEval introduces a structured, scalable evaluation process. Unlike traditional benchmarks, it allows for flexible, user-defined settings, making it especially useful for critical applications while offering valuable insights.

3 Methodology

SallyEval evaluates LLMs using a structured benchmarking pipeline that ensures consistency, reproducibility and adaptability (Fig. 1).

- **Step 1: LLM Selection (Hidden from User)** The system automatically selects two LLMs for evaluation. This selection follows an adaptive sampling strategy (see Section 2) that prioritizes comparisons involving models with uncertain rankings or limited evaluation data, ensuring a more accurate ranking over time.
- **Step 2: User Poses a Question** Once the models are selected, the user initiates the conversation by submitting a query. Each LLM independently generates a response within its own chat session, allowing the user to engage with both models separately.
- **Step 3: Dynamic Chat Interaction** The user can continue the conversation with both models, exchanging messages iteratively. Since the chat histories develop independently for each model, their responses may differ in tone, coherence, and contextual adaptation, reflecting the variations in their conversational abilities.
- **Step 4: Response Evaluation** At any point during the conversation, the user can evaluate the responses by selecting the one they perceive as superior. To provide further insights, the user can also assign a numerical rating from 1 to 5 for each evaluation category.
- **Step 5: LLM Identities Revealed** After submitting their evaluation, the system reveals the identity of each LLM, allowing users to see which model generated which response. This approach prevents bias during the assessment phase while enabling post-evaluation review of model performance.
- **Step 6: Iterative Process** Users may initiate a new question and repeat the evaluation process as needed, ensuring continuous assessment and refinement of model rankings based on real user interactions.

Fig. 1: Flowchart of the SallyEval Evaluation Pipeline for A/B Testing

3.1 Custom Evaluation Configurations

While SallyEval allows for predefined evaluation categories such as accuracy, clarity, and contextual relevance, these serve as qualitative assessment criteria rather than static benchmarks. However, users can define domain-specific benchmarks by uploading question datasets, which will be answered by all LLMs in the system, enabling a more structured evaluation process. Additionally, users can set custom evaluation categories for each benchmark, allowing for tailored assessments based on specific domain requirements.

- **Custom benchmark categories:** Upload custom question datasets to create structured evaluation scenarios for all LLMs.
- **Custom evaluation categories:** Define specific rating criteria that can vary based on the selected question dataset (benchmark).
- **Manual LLM selection:** Compare specific LLM pairs using a **blind evaluation process** (model identities remain hidden until submission).

3.2 Evaluation Metrics

Evaluations capture both quantitative and qualitative metrics, including response time and detected language. User assessments provide additional insights through pairwise evaluations, where evaluators compare responses and select the preferred one. Along with their selection, users also provide a numerical rating (1 to 5) for each evaluation category, offering a structured justification for their choice of LLM.

SallyEval tracks comparison counts and updates model rankings using the Elo rating system, applying larger score adjustments for unexpected wins. Each evaluation is timestamped, allowing for the analysis of performance trends over time.

The Elo rating system updates both the winner’s and loser’s scores after each comparison using the following formulas:

$$E_{\text{winner,new}} = E_{\text{winner,old}} + K \times (1 - P_{\text{winner}}) \quad (1)$$

$$E_{\text{loser,new}} = E_{\text{loser,old}} + K \times (0 - P_{\text{loser}}) \quad (2)$$

where:

- $E_{\text{winner,new}}$ and $E_{\text{loser,new}}$ are the updated Elo scores for the winning and losing models.
- $E_{\text{winner,old}}$ and $E_{\text{loser,old}}$ are the previous Elo scores.
- K is the scaling factor that controls the sensitivity of rating adjustments.
- P_{winner} and P_{loser} are the expected probabilities of winning for each model, computed as:

$$P = \frac{1}{1 + 10^{(E_{\text{opponent}} - E_{\text{current}})/400}} \quad (3)$$

This ensures that models with lower initial ratings gain more Elo points when winning against higher-ranked models, leading to a more dynamic and adaptive ranking system. The structured collection of evaluation data enables a deeper understanding of user preferences and model effectiveness, supporting ongoing improvements to benchmarking methodologies.

3.3 Implementation Details

SallyEval is implemented as a web-based evaluation platform using a client-server architecture. The frontend is built with React, selected for its component-based architecture as it promotes reusability and maintainability, making it easier to scale the platform as new features are introduced.

The backend is built with Flask, a Python web framework chosen for its simplicity, extensive libraries, and strong community support. Python’s flexibility enables efficient handling of API requests. The backend contains RESTful API endpoints, with WebSocket integration enabling real-time updates where necessary. SallyEval uses MongoDB Atlas to store and manage all collections efficiently. The database is optimized for fast read and write operations, with indexed fields improving query speed and ensuring the system remains scalable as evaluation data grows.

4 Use Case: Migration Support

SALLY [9] is an AI chatbot designed to assist immigrants in Greece. The chatbot is built on a RAG architecture to combine information retrieval with generative AI, ensuring accurate, context-aware responses. This approach ensures that answers are grounded in factual sources while minimizing the risk of misinformation. SALLY primarily sources information from migration.gov.gr, the official website for migration policies in Greece. By continuously updating its knowledge base, SALLY ensures that its responses remain accurate, relevant, and aligned with official regulations.

However, evaluating the performance of the underlying LLMs used in SALLY presents unique challenges that traditional LLM evaluation frameworks do not fully address. As previously mentioned, existing benchmarks often assess general-purpose reasoning, factual correctness, or coding abilities, but they fail to capture domain-specific factors which are critical for applications such as assisting migrants. A challenge that SallyEval is built to address.

4.1 Dataset

The dataset was built using real-world scenarios that migrants often encounter, ensuring the content was both relevant and actionable. The benchmarks address two critical aspects of migrant support:

Legal & Immigration Procedures This benchmark assesses the ability of LLMs to deliver accurate, legally sound, and actionable advice on immigration laws and procedures in Greece. The dataset was curated using questions from legal forums, government sources, and real-world queries from migrants. For example, a common question might be, *"How do I apply for asylum in Greece?"* Given the complexity of legal processes, ensuring accurate and up-to-date responses is crucial. Misinterpretations can lead to severe consequences, such as deportation or invalid applications. Additionally, the dynamic nature of immigration regulations requires LLMs to provide reliable guidance despite frequent legislative changes. Furthermore, the procedural steps involved in immigration are often complex and bureaucratic, necessitating clear, step-by-step instructions to avoid confusion and errors.

Practical Assistance & Social Integration This benchmark evaluates the LLM's ability to provide practical, culturally relevant and accessible support to migrants adapting to life in Greece. The dataset includes typical questions about daily life, such as housing, healthcare, education and social services. For instance, a common query might be, *"How do I register my child for school in Greece?"*. In addition to legal guidance, this benchmark emphasizes the importance of addressing everyday challenges. Migrants often face unique cultural and linguistic barriers, requiring clear and culturally aware responses. Effective support in this area can significantly impact a migrant's ability to navigate their new environment and integrate into the local community.

4.2 Data Collection

The dataset consisted of a total of 100 chats, which included not only initial questions but also follow-up questions when necessary to ensure a comprehensive evaluation. All nine authors, each with a technical background, participated in the evaluation process, contributing a diverse range of perspectives and expertise. Evaluators also impersonated migrants to better assess SALLY's real-world effectiveness.

While the number of LLMs used in the evaluation was relatively small (three in total), the aim was to present the potential of this evaluation framework. In future versions, more LLM options will be incorporated to expand the evaluation scope and further refine the system's capabilities.

Through these evaluation tools, we were able to measure and compare not only the LLM's performance but also the chatbot's user satisfaction and real-world effectiveness in assisting migrants.

Table 1: Performance Metrics of Models

Model	ELO	Win %	Lose %	Rating
4o-Latest	1050.63	64	36	4.4
Flash-2o	960.83	44	56	4.19
Claude 3.7 Sonnet	988.54	47	53	4.0

Fig. 2: Comparison of Evaluation Scores

4.3 Results

The data (Table 1 and Fig. 2) indicate that **GPT4o-Latest** outperformed the other models across most metrics, achieving the highest **Elo score of 1050.63** and a **win rate of 64%**, demonstrating its overall superiority in human preference-based evaluations. Notably, it received the highest **helpfulness rating (4.6)**, suggesting that users found its responses particularly useful in guiding them through legal and practical procedures. **Claude 3.7 Sonnet** performed competitively, obtaining the highest **accuracy (4.5)** and **clarity (4.5)** scores, indicating its strength in delivering precise and well-structured information. However, its **lower completeness score (3.75)** suggests that its responses may sometimes lack detail or fail to provide comprehensive answers.

The performance metrics in Table 1 include the Elo score, calculated using the method described in Section 3.2, where each comparison updates the score based on the expected win probability. Win and Lose percentages represent the share of pairwise comparisons each model won or lost, respectively. The Rating is the average score assigned by evaluators across the qualitative categories reflecting overall user satisfaction.

Meanwhile, **Flash-2o** showed a balanced performance with a clarity rating of **4.3** and a helpfulness score of **4.4**, but its **lower accuracy (3.8)** and **Elo**

rating (960.83) indicate that it was generally less preferred compared to the other models. Overall, based on our benchmark results and SallyEval’s current Elo-based ranking system, **4o-Latest** would be selected as the top-performing model, demonstrating strong user satisfaction across both legal and practical queries. **Claude 3.7 Sonnet** remains a strong contender in accuracy and clarity but may require improvements in completeness.

4.4 LLM Selection

While SallyEval ranks LLMs based on Elo scores, final model selection could also take qualitative insights into account. Users may examine evaluation results such as average ratings in the feedback categories. In future versions, a weighted scoring system could combine Elo with user preferences to enable more personalized model selection.

$$S = 0.6E + 0.4R \quad (4)$$

where E is the Elo score and R is the average user rating (1–5 scale).

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This study introduces SallyEval, a scalable framework for benchmarking LLMs using structured A/B testing and data-driven assessments. Unlike traditional methods, SallyEval supports customized evaluations, making it ideal for domain-specific use cases. In our evaluation, the top-performing model, GPT4o-Latest, achieved an Elo score of 1050.63, with a 64% win rate.

However, the framework also comes with certain limitations. For example, evaluator subjectivity and potential biases can influence results, especially when user feedback is inconsistent. Additionally, maintaining up-to-date rankings in a rapidly evolving LLM landscape presents ongoing challenges, especially when new models are introduced frequently.

Future work will focus on addressing these limitations and expanding the framework’s capabilities. Key priorities include integrating bias detection mechanisms to improve fairness, automating re-evaluation strategies to keep rankings current, expanding multilingual evaluation support to ensure fair assessments across languages, and integrating more LLMs to provide up-to-date performance comparisons. Furthermore, we aim to introduce more dynamic benchmarking configurations, such as weighting evaluation criteria based on task-specific priorities, enabling more targeted and context-aware assessments.

By tackling these challenges, SallyEval will continue to evolve into a more robust, fair, and insightful evaluation tool for large language models.

Acknowledgments. This research project is carried out within the framework of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan Greece 2.0, funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU (Implementation body: HFRI, Project Number: 15010).

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